

Career Growth of Non-Commissioned Women Officers and Their Organizational Commitment

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ABSTRACT

This study determined which domain in career growth of non-commissioned women officers best influences their organizational commitment in Palawan, Philippines. The study employed the quantitative, non-experimental research design using the correlational technique. The respondents were the 182 non-commissioned women officers determined using the universal sampling procedure. Pearson r and regression analysis were the statistical tools used in this study. Moreover, adapted survey questionnaire was used for career growth and organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. The result

showed that the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment were both high. Further, data show that there was a significant relationship between career growth and organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. In its singular capacity, job rotation best influences the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers.

Keywords: *Criminal Justice, Career Growth, Organizational Commitments, Correlational Design, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Women are now accepted to be competitive just like men globally. But there are cases that they are being questioned for doing so especially regarding their relationship and connection with their organizations. A number of police agencies face many problems regarding employees' commitment towards organization. For instance, in the United Kingdom, there is lack of organizational commitment among police officers as evidence of the slow progress in policing since gender differences are considered as factor (Dick & Metcalfe, 2007; Segrave, 2014). Moreover, in the Philippines, there are problems involving perceptions of women police officers' stereotypical roles in an organization where almost all members are male, believing their physical capabilities are being underestimated and given less challenging assignments or positions (De Guzman & Frank, 2004) which are related to their organizational commitment.

Organizational commitments were positively related to career growth (Weng & McElroy, 2012). Weng, McElroy, Morrow, and Liu (2010), said that career growth is merely achieving career goals, improving professionalism and receiving rewards through promotion or compensation from it. Moreover, in making job decisions, career growth is one of the first concerns of many and if disregarded will destroy the relationship of employees with their organizations (Hu, Weng, & Yang, 2008; Chen, Hou, Li, Lovelace, Liu, & Wang, 2015). It is also considered to be a reinforcement to the organization (Wang, Weng, McElroy, Ashkanasy, & Lievens,

2014). Meanwhile, employees usually want to have greater control over their career and look for opportunities that will develop their skills and ensure employability (Savickas, 2012) which affirmed that career growth increases employees' commitment if given attention in an organization. The constant findings of previous results study (Weng et al. 2010; Juhdi, Pa'wan & Hansaram, 2013) suggest that career growth should not be taken for granted as the higher it is provided the higher the commitment of the personnel towards the success of the organization.

Most studies examined the perceptions of employees towards their career growth and organizational commitment (Weng & McElroy, 2010). Results indicate that career growth is positively related with organizational commitment, which means that if employees perceive that their career growth increased they are more likely committed with the organization, they will also improve their job performance and expect for higher level of job satisfaction. Moreover, one of the determinants of a sense of belonging, commitment, and satisfaction is career growth. Its implies that achieving work goals, fair treatment, appreciation, and rewards to efforts and sacrifices increase the sense of belonging, commitment, and satisfaction (Ku Daud, 2014).

The researcher has not come across on a study that dealt with the influence of career growth of non-commissioned women officers on their sense of organizational commitment in Palawan. It is in the context that the researcher is interested to determine whether their career growth affect their organizational commitment as this can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop intervention schemes to improve their job performance, thus, the need to conduct this study. The findings of the research will help heads in the organization of the Philippine National Police in making the best method on how to encourage the women police officers to do their job with organizational commitment.

Research Objective

This study was conducted to determine which domain in career growth of non-commissioned women officers' best influences the organizational commitment. More specifically, this study endeavored to attain the following objectives:

1. To assess the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers regarding:
 - a. career goal progress;
 - b. professional ability development;
 - c. promotion speed;
 - d. remuneration growth;
 - e. promotion equity; and
 - f. job rotation.
2. To ascertain the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers regarding:
 - a. affective commitment;
 - b. continuance commitment; and
 - c. normative commitment.
3. To determine the significant relationship between career growth of non-commissioned women officer and their organizational commitment.
4. To determine which domain of career growth best influences the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers.

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at $\alpha= 0.05$ level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between career growth of non-commissioned women officer and their organizational commitment.
2. There is no domain of career growth best influence the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers.

Review of Related Literature

Various readings from different books, theses, and internet of different authors that have a bearing on the present study are in this section. The researcher focuses on career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment.

The independent variable is career growth of non-commissioned women officers and has the following indicators; career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth, promotion equity, and job rotation (Ku Daud, 2014). On the other hand, the dependent variable is organizational commitment with the following indicators; affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Anttila, 2014).

Career Growth

Various studies have focused on the concept of career growth, which has two ways to achieve. One is structural advancement to where the employees are likely entitled to promotion; another is content advancement as to where the employees earned experiences and skills within his or current position. Relatively, it is defined as the likelihood that the employees get promotion and develop through experiences in the performance of his or her task in his or her current position within the organization (Weer, 2006; Karavardar, 2014). Moreover, career growth is also described as employees' view of the opportunity for development and advancement in their organization (Jans, 1989; Spagnoli & Weng, 2017).

In connection, career goal progress is the employees' realization that the present jobs are relevant and provide opportunities to a set career goals. In New York Police Department, for instance, female officers are observed to have little progress in positions (Guajardo, 2014). As suggested in surveys carried out by Weng et al. (2010) and Weng and McElroy, (2012) career goal progress is positively related to organizational commitment. It helps the employees feel the security in their position within their organization (Wang et al. 2014). However, in the result study of Ku Daud, (2014) career goal progress and remuneration growth have no significant relationship with organizational commitment. Nevertheless, promotion equity, professional ability development, promotion speed and job rotation are related.

Further, according to the survey, career goal progress had relatively higher scores in Korean employees than Chinese employees. They also mentioned that career growth scale could be used regardless of cultural background (Kim, Rhee, Jung, Daeyeon, Lee, Lee & Ha 2015). Likewise, Nawaz and Pangil (2015) found out that career growth is related to turnover intention. However, they pointed out that career goal progress does not influence turnover intention in singular capacity which implies that there other factors of career growth that may affect the work support and escalate retention of competent employees (Yang, Liu, Liu, & Zhang, 2015).

In contrary, in the study of Biswakarma (2016), organizational career growth has no significant relationship with employees' turnover intentions (Karimi & Rahimi, 2020; Weng et al. 2010; Weng and McElroy (2012). However, he found career goal progress as a factor that has a direct high impact on employees' turnover intentions in Nepalese context.

Meanwhile, professional ability development is one of the factors used to determine career growth. It is ensuing when the employees are encouraged continuously to gain new job-related skills, new job-related knowledge and accumulate richer work experiences (Karavardar, 2014; Spagnoli, Presti & Buono, 2019). In this study, professional ability development or most commonly referred as training is defined as

the development of knowledge, skills, and abilities of the employees as needed in the performance of their work (Ku Daud, 2014; Nordhaug, 1989; Nouri & Parker 2013).

In the survey conducted by Reyes and Conde, (2017) in the Philippines, professional ability development among nurses was perceived high as that employee's present job encourages them to continuously gain new job-related skills, new job-related knowledge, accumulate richer work experiences and improve continuously in their professional capabilities. Consequently, it is practical that organizations should determine the appropriateness between employee's expectation in his or her career and the organizational development opportunities so that connecting of career goals towards success can be established (Wang et al., 2014).

Further, in the study of Dong, Seo and Bartol (2013), development job experience is related to advancement potential of an employee as long as it boosts pleasant feeling. It is an indication that career development support will make the employees believe that the organization provides them career growth opportunities, which positively affect their organizational commitment (Kohlmeyer, Parker & Sincich, 2017).

On the other hand, for Ng and Feldman (2014) career obstacle with low emotional stability, low work engagement and low supervisor support were associated with subjective career success. All of the foregoing results were supported by the idea of Kehoe and Wright (2013) that the employees who are committed are felt obliges to return the benefits to their employers.

Moreover, in the study of Karavardar (2014), professional ability development has strong influences on turnover intentions of the employees. In connection, the said domain found positively influenced affective organizational commitment. Additionally, Wang et al. (2014) demonstrated that professional ability development not only provides skills and training for employees, especially women, but also broaden their capacity to share information, ideas, and suggestions that will help the functioning of the organization. In short, professional ability developments improve the potentials of the employees in doing their job within the organization.

Furthermore, promotion speed is the third domain of career growth. It is defining as the probability of being promoted from one rank or position to a higher rank or position. Accordingly, by nature people want recognition in the form of promotion in an organization (Ku Daud, 2014).

A survey carried out by Reyes and Conde (2017), found that promotion speed is one of the factors that extrinsically motivated nurses in the Philippines to continue to post graduate education. In addition, Weng et al. (2010) study result in Chinese companies showed that promotion speed is a factor that affects organizational commitment.

However, in the study of Weng and McElroy (2012), they put promotion speed and remuneration together to reward and found out that both factors may not affect the turnover intentions and affective occupational commitment. This somewhat supplementary with the study results of Karavardar (2014) to where promotion speeds is not related to the intent to leave. Nevertheless, in survey of Nawaz and Pangil

(2015) in private universities of Pakistan, argued that promotion speed has strong influence on turnover intentions, which indicates that employers should prioritize promotion speed domain as employees who are typically working hard yet not promoted to higher ranks usually decline their commitment. Moreover, Maia, Bastos, and Solinger (2016) support that commitment to work predicted employees' initiative and productivity.

A survey showed that Korean employees perceived promotion speed high than Chinese employees (Kim et al. 2015). It also confirmed that the four facets of career growth include career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed and remuneration growth (Nawaz & Pangil, 2015) are more applicable in Korean employees. Likewise, in the study of Biswakarma (2016) in Nepalese Private Commercial Banks, the domains of career growth used are career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed and remuneration growth (Li, 2018; Weng et al. 2010) though the study proposed the clubbing of promotion speed and remuneration growth (Weng & McElroy (2012).

Furthermore, Ku Daud (2014) alleged that the organizations with a good human resource management practices for career growth are more likely successful than ever. The said success will lead them to provide more training and promotion opportunities that will encourage the personnel to be more committed with their job and to the organization. Even though it showed from previous research that low commitment will result to high staff turnover, it is revealed that some employees who are not committed will remain in the organization as they consider that it was somewhat too late for them to change their career path.

Continuously, the fourth domain of career growth is remuneration growth. In this study, it is defined as the employees' beliefs that they get a fair compensation commensurate to their effort and sacrifices within the organization (Ku Daud, 2014). Weng et al. (2010) and Weng and McElroy (2012) both indicated study results that remuneration growth has positive impact towards commitment. They highlighted career goal progress and rewards (promotion and remuneration) as the highest factor associated with organizational commitment.

Relatively, Weng et al. (2010) added that salary is the reflection how employer evaluate the employee's performance. Blau (1964) and Rousseau (1989) also indicated that in psychological contract and balance social exchange, it is natural that employees have expectations of fair returns from their employers (Ku Daud, 2014). Henceforth, if the expectations are not fulfilling, this may result in reduction of commitment and performance (Festing & Schafer, 2014).

Subsequently, in the study of Reyes and Conde (2017) in the Philippines, it argued higher salary as factor that boosts employees to be extrinsically motivated to continue educating themselves about the organization they serve. They signified that remuneration growth is perceived by staff nurses among healthcare organization in Philippines at the moderate level. They also suggested that employers should make sure that employees understand the promotion procedure and reward administration of the organization so that they can manage the latter's expectations and lessen their frustration about promotion and salary growth.

In the study of Hui (2014) in Malaysia, found that education level is the factor that predicts barriers to women career advancement. Thus, remuneration growth influences the performance of women career path within the organization.

Equally important is the study of Karavardar (2014) in Turkey which shows that career growth is not a factor that may affect turnover intentions (Lu, Sun & Du, 2015) yet he presented that remuneration growth has strong influence with the intention to leave the organization. This research asserted that the better the remuneration growth provided by the organization, the lesser the chances that the employees will think of leaving their job. Porter and Steers (1973) supported it by the theory of met expectations.

Moreover, even Biswakrma (2016) study found organizational career growth negatively related to turnover intentions though he pointed out that remuneration growth is a factor with high impact on employee's turnover intentions. He also concluded that there should be a strong feeling of consideration to psychological contract of the employees in implementing organizational career growth as policy towards career growth is one of the concerns of the employees especially those who have expectations of progress and growths on their career (Bedeian, Kemery, & Pizzolatto 1991; Okurame, 2012).

Conversely, in the study of Nawaz and Pangil (2015), found that career growth is positively related to turnover intentions. He also emphasized that remuneration growth strongly influences the employee's intention to leave the organization. Henceforth, if the employees perceive that they have the better salary, rewards and benefits from the employers, then, the better their organizational attachment and the turnover intention is reduced.

The fifth domain of career growth is promotion equity. Promotion equity is the perception of the employees that the organizations they work in have fair policies, rules, and regulations and procedures in making just decisions on promotion. It is needed to be focused, as it will help increase organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Further, even if there are no competitive salaries as a reward for the employees, there should be a fair treatment in promotion and career opportunities as it is expected by employees all the time (Ku Daud, 2014).

In the study of Izquierdo, Moscoso, and Villagrasa (2012), the fairer promotion methods are those that are based on performances. In the results of the study in Malaysia, show that inequality in promotion decision may affect the employee's performance towards work. Likewise, the turnover intention is also high, especially among young managerial staff (Wan, Sulaiman, & Omar, 2012).

Consequently, good quality of work life increase performances, fulfillment, effectiveness, and commitment, lessen the number of non-attendance and the intent to leave the organization. It could be achieved if the human resource management will prioritize a reasonable salary and rewards, clear promotion policies, better communication and supervision, more stable work schedules, and introducing non-smoking work areas (Wan & Chan, 2013).

However, in Mosadeghrad (2013) study results in Iran, show that the key to the better quality of work life of employees is strong support from the management. He added that employers should pay

attention to how to improve the ‘working conditions, benefits, and promotion equity’ of the employees. To sum up, promotion should be fair as it is significantly related to job satisfaction and performance (Khan, Nawaz, Aleem, & Hamed, 2012).

Promotion fairness has the positive effect on organizational commitment. Whereas, when the employees know that there is fairness in the promotion process within their organization they are more inspired to work hard (Ma, Tang & Yan, 2015). Success will be achieved if the person believes that the promotion system is fair enough. Besides, if the company or agencies want to improve the quality of their performance, they should start with refining the promotion and merits system. For the promotion and merit system to be successful, the employees should believe that it is appropriate and fair enough (Gonzalez, Liu, & Shu, 2012).

Further, in the survey conducted in UK companies by Meyer and Smith (2000), show that fair and supportive career development is factor that may affect commitment. Likewise, Amin, Ismail, Rasid, and Selemani (2014) indicated in their study that rightful compensation is significantly related to organizational commitment.

Equally important are the results study of the Hossein, Foumany, Valeh, and Davoudi (2012) in North Khorasan, Iran, argued that promotion system have impact in employees commitment. Thus, the organization should use the appropriate promotion scheme to achieve the desired results.

The sixth domain of career growth is job rotation. It is defined as the process of transferring people from one field of work to another or from one area, division, or unit to another to broaden the knowledge and skills in various specializations, to improve their discretion and flexibility while promoting high morale within the organization (Ku Daud 2014). According to the research conducted by Khan, Rasli, Yusoff, Ahmed, Rehman, and Khan (2014) in Pakistan, job rotation significantly related to organizational commitment. They emphasized that job rotation is related to commitment and increase the performance level of employees.

Likewise, in the study of Saravani and Abbasi (2013) in Iran, illustrated that job rotation will not just increase job satisfaction but also increase the competences of employees. Further, job rotation influences job performance because of the mediation of job satisfaction and skills variation.

Equally important is the study of Chen, Wu, Chang, and Lin (2013) among nurses in Taiwan hospitals, wherein they found out that job rotation has a positive effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Their study illustrated that job rotation is used as an operative tool to improve the performances and competencies of nurses and reduce the number of turnover. Job rotation will not only increase the organizational commitment of the employee but also increase the skills, knowledge, and flexibility of the nurses to work. To sum up, job rotation will help enhance the very central tool of the employees in doing their job, the discretion and knowledge in the organization (Ganter & Hecker, 2014).

Consequently, there is a profession where the workers are frequently transferred that somewhat may result in stress and affect their motivation. However, in the study of Sanali, Bahron, and Dousin (2013)

in Malaysia, job rotation is a factor that may affect motivation and negatively related to stress. Besides, job rotation have impact to employees' performances regarding productivity, improvements of skills, and training, detecting, and correcting wrongs within the organization (Oparanma & Nwaeke, 2015). It is a good solution to reduce error and improves employees' career (Kwon & Kim, 2014).

Moreover, in the study of Ajusa and Atambo (2016) in Kenya, the employer tool to motivate employees and train different skills is job rotation. Likewise, in the study of Twei & Saina (2015) in Kenya, job rotation affected the performance of the employees. Based on the findings, its contribution to the employees' performances is 55.29 percent. Thus, job rotation must be included in the priorities of the organization

Organizational Commitment

The concept of organizational commitment refers to the reaction of an individual towards the characteristics of their organization (Cook and Wall, 1980). However, for Suliman and Iles (2000) it is a motivating force in every employee's performance.

Commitment manifests itself in three relatively distinct manners. According to Meyer and Allen (1900), these include affective, continuance and normative commitment (Mguqulwa, 2009). According to McMahon (2007), the above three-component model is used to determine the level the organizational commitment of the employees.

The first manifestation is affective commitment. It refers to the degree to which a person enjoys his or her membership to the organization and identifies the organization problems as his or her own. It also explained the sense of belonging in which the organization and the personal goal and values are the same. Similarly, it is related to the organizational identification and job performance while not related to the intent to leave (Lam & Liu, 2014). According to Meyer, Allen and Smith's (1993) if the need for fulfilment in the experiences is achieved, commitment increases which shows that satisfied employees more likely value and give efforts towards organization growth (Ku Daud, 2014).

In the research study in China, they found out that affective commitment can be associated with career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed and remuneration growth (Weng et al. 2010). Employers should provide jobs and experiences that will help employees meet their career expectation in terms of their career and abilities (Weng & McElroy, 2012).

Career growth is the factor that is considered always, as it influences the emotional aspect of the organization, the affective domain (Nouri & Parker, 2013). It is supported in the research study of Albdour and Altarawneh (2014) in the banks of Jordan, to where the frontline employees who have the high job and organizational engagement will usually have the high affective commitment and normative commitment.

The second manifestation of organizational commitment is the continuance commitment. This commitment emphasized that years of service and investment control the person to leave the organization (Reichers, 1985) because of the idea that when they do that everything that they earned from it like retirement benefits are nontransferable (Ku Daud, 2014). Meyer and Allen (1997) further explained that

this type of commitment makes it hard for the employees not to be loyal to the organization. It leaves for another cause as if they do so the hardship and effort they have already given to become part of it and to be qualified to the benefits they aim from the beginning will be forfeited (Lambert, Kim, Kelley & Hogan, 2013; Wallace, 1997).

Moreover, in the study of Sood, Bakhshi, and Singh (2015) among 110 Anganwadi workers found that life satisfaction promotes continuance commitments. In other words, employees who are satisfied in their life are more likely to continue to serve the organization. Also, it is believe that a satisfied employees with their lives usually treated others equally good including their organization. Life satisfaction indicates happy life. Once a person is happy, she is more creative and productive. On the other hand, unhappy person may become demoralized and ineffective in their work (Erdogan, Bauer, Truxillo, & Mansfield, 2012).

On the contrary, previous research study on correctional staff life satisfaction at two Midwestern prisons, one private and one public, argued that continuance commitment is not related to life satisfaction (Lambert et al. 2013). They also said that continuance commitment might decrease life satisfaction. It means that continuance commitment is often undesirable (Sinclair, Leo, & Wright, 2005) as it is not only unrelated to life satisfaction but also to job performance. In other words, whenever the employees perceived the high possibility of losing benefits, seniority status, and gratuities, they are more likely give up and resign from their work (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001).

Moreover, regarding career growth, career goal progress, promotion speed, and remuneration are positively associated with continuance commitment (Weng et al. 2010), which simply means that promotion opportunities and good salary and benefits will help establish continuance commitment. In other words, they find it costly to leave the organization because of those chances. However, when the benefits and opportunities are low, this will be easy for the employees for turnover (Weng & McElroy, 2012; Wasti, Peterson, Breitsohl, Cohen, Jørgensen, Rodrigues, Weng, & Xu, 2016).

In the study of Miao, Newman, Schwarz, and Xu (2014) in China, found that servant leadership has no impact to continuance commitment while strongly influences affective and normative commitment. It shows that civil servants are not influenced whether the cost of leaving the organization are high or low. In other words, they continue working because they considered their organization is their own and obliged to serve it better. According to Meyer and Allen (1990) somehow, this is because of the two variables accompanied by continuance commitment, the perceived cost of leaving, and the availability of alternatives.

Moreover, Albdour and Altarawneh (2014) in Jordan, spell out high job engagement will positively affect continuance commitment. It is related to the study results of Bakker and Demerouti (2008) that employees who physically and psychologically active in doing their job were reported to have low continuance commitment. Consequently, some researchers questioned the nature of continuance commitment whether it consists of high sacrifices or low alternatives sub-dimensions (Jaros & Culpepper, 2014).

The last manifestations of organizational commitment are the normative commitments. It is the feeling that the person must repay the organization that employed them (Bolon, 1993; Mohamed & Anisa,

2012). In 1982, Wiener added that this term refers to “generalized value of loyalty and duty” (Ilyas, 2013). Meyer and Allen’s (1991) statement is similar to some author’s definition that normative commitment is having “a feeling of obligation”. A person is tied up to the organization once he or she has this, that no matter what happens to the said organization, that person will remain loyal and obliged to serve the organization (Ku Daud, 2014).

In the study of Yucel, McMillan, and Richard (2014) in Turkey, confirmed that employee trust, satisfaction, flexibility, solidarity and participation in decision making indirectly influence normative commitment through affective commitment (Mabasa, 2018). Moreover, in a survey conducted by Khan, Khan, Khan, Nawaz, and Bakht Yar (2013) in Pakistan indicated that sense of belonging to an employee to the organization is known as normative commitment. Further, a survey conducted by Choong, Wong and Lau (2012) in Malaysia, suggested that a faithful employee usually has normative commitment. It shows that normative commitment is more an advantage when experienced as a moral duty (Jackson, Meyer & Wang, 2013; Meyer & Parfyonova, 2010).

Furthermore, in the study of Tolentino (2013) in the Philippines, found that academic and administrative personnel remain in the university because they must do so. It led to strong loyalty to the organization. This loyalty of the employee obliges them to remain with the organization (Meyer et al. 1993). One of the bases of loyalty of an employee to the organization is their capacity to be satisfied that includes personal growth and job security at work (Gong, Law, Chang & Xin, 2009; Hackman & Oldham, 1975). In addition, they revealed that normative commitment and affective commitment is stronger among academic than administrative personnel (Ku Daud, 2014).

On the other hand, continuance commitment is stronger among administrative than academic personnel. In other words, the differences in the level of commitment show that there should be a separate career growth for academic and administrative personnel. Conversely, age provides expertise which is a factor that helps increase normative commitment (Bal, De Lange, Zacher, & Van der Heijden, 2012; Cleveland, Fisher, & Walters, 2016).

Correlation between Measures

There have been some researches about the relationship between career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment. For instance, in the study of Weng and Mc Elroy (2012), they highlighted that there is a significant relationship between career growth and organizational commitments. Likewise, Ganter and Hecker (2014) confirmed that organizational commitment is positively related to career growth perhaps enhances the very important tool of the employees in doing their job, the discretion, and knowledge (Cai, Ocampo, Restubog, Kiazad, Deen, & Li, (2017).

In the same manner, according to Ku Daud (2014) most studies that examined the perceptions of employees towards their career growth and organizational commitment support the positive relationship of career growth with organizational commitment. Which simply means that if employees perceive that their career growth increased, they are more likely committed to the organization, they will also improve their

job performance and expect for higher level of job satisfaction. Besides, one of the determinants of a sense of belonging, commitment, and satisfaction is career growth. It indicates that achieving work goals, fair treatment, appreciation, and rewards to efforts and sacrifices increase the sense of belonging, commitment, and satisfaction.

Meanwhile, Savickas (2012) implicated that employees usually want to have greater control over their career and look for opportunities that will develop their skills and ensure employability which affirmed that career growth increases employee's commitment if given attention in an organization (Wang et al., 2014). The constant findings of previous results study (Weng et al. 2010; Juhdi, Pa'wan & Hansaram, 2013) suggest that career growth should not be taken for granted as the higher it is provided the higher the commitment of the personnel towards the success of the organization.

In connection, some studies determine the influence of career growth to organizational commitment (Karavardar, 2014). For instance, Nawaz and Pangil (2015) posit that career growth had significant relationships with turnover intention which implies that additional opportunities for career growth within the organization may strengthen employees' commitment and increase retention (Yang et al. 2015).

However, in the study of Karavardar (2014) among auditors in Turkey, he stated that there is no buffering effect of organizational commitment on the relationship between organizational career growth and turnover intention (Nawaz & Pangil, 2015). Moreover, Biswakarma (2016), alleged that organizational career growth is negatively associated with employees' turnover intentions (Weng et al. (2010; Weng & McElroy, 2012). He also concluded that there should be a strong feeling of consideration to psychological contract of the employees in implementing organizational career growth as policy towards career growth is one of the concerns of the employees especially those who have expectations of progress and growths on their career (Bedeian et al. 1991; Okurame, 2012).

Furthermore, it is practical that organizations should determine the appropriateness between employee's expectation in his or her career and the organizational development opportunities so that connecting of career goals towards success can be established (Ku Daud, 2014; Wang et al., 2014). As such, career development support will convince the employees that the organization they serve provides them career growth opportunities, which positively affect their organizational commitment (Kohlmeyer et al., 2017). The statement agrees with the study results of Weng et al. (2010), who demonstrates that lack of career growth experience will usually result in a failed employee's commitment to the organization.

In summary, the preceding presentation and discussion of various literatures have helped in bringing into focus the two important variables such as career growth and organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. The related literature has also helped the researcher in the construction of the research instrument used in the gathering of data.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the proposition of Weng et al. (2010), that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and career growth. They concluded that organizational commitment can be influenced by career growth as an additive rather than a multiplicative manner.

Consequently, an organization must have employees who believe and accept the organizational goals and enjoys being part of achieving it (Porter, Steers, Mowday & Boulian, 1974). They also explain that it is hard for the employees not to be loyal to the organization or leave it for another cause as the hardship and effort they had already given to become part of it and to be qualified to the benefits they aim from the beginning will be forfeited (Lambert et al. 2013; Wallace, 1997). Likewise, a person is tied up to the organization once she has commitment, that no matter what happens to the said organization, that person will remain loyal and obliged to serve the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1997).

Moreover, career growth plays an important role in organizational commitment (Weng et al. 2010). For instance, career development support will convince the employees that the organization they serve provides them career growth opportunities, which positively affect their organizational commitment (Kohlmeyer et al. 2017). The above statements are supported by Chen et al. (2015), that career growth is more needed today to develop organizational commitment among employees as it is a factor for the changing economy.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study is shown in Figure 1. The independent variable which is career growth was taken from the study of Ku Daud (2014) and has the following indicators: career goal progress which refers to an increase in the achievement of career goals; professional ability development which denotes to the development of the knowledge, skills, and abilities that employees require performing their tasks competently (Ku Daud, 2014; Nordhaug 1989; Nouri & Parker 2013); promotion speed is when the police officer climbed the ladder of her career; remuneration growth is the payment or reward for the performance or effort of the office; promotion equity is the natural to desire to be treated and compensated in a fair manner by the employer; and lastly, job rotation is when the employee is being transferred to another area or field of work or assignment.

The dependent variable is the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers which was taken from the study of Meyer and Allen (1997) and has the following indicators; affective is the desire to work with the organization, while continuance is the need to work with the organization and normative is the obligation to work with the organization. It was viewed that concept of organizational commitment is the single dimension, based on an attitudinal perspective, embracing identification, involvement, and loyalty (Porter et al. 1974; Shirali, Feizi, & Aliour, 2013).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Significance of the Study

The global importance of this study is that when there is good career growth there will be development in the skills and the capacity of the employees in doing their job, the desire to work with the organization to achieve the goals also increases (Wang et al., 2014),

On the other side, the social value is to understand how career growth can affect the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers in Palawan and seeks to understand whether it slows performance or what extent it can improve performance of the non-commissioned women officers. Employees with more career growth are more committed and give extra effort towards organizational success (Savickas, 2012)

Likewise, the findings of the study may be beneficial to the Philippine National Police officials, uniformed personnel, and non-uniformed personnel who may use the results of the study in formulating and developing a system and a program on how to motivate police officers to become more committed in work and in the organization. Likewise, the study may provide feedback to the management of PNP program officers concerning organizational commitment of the employees. Moreover, this may serve a point of reference in selecting the most appropriate factors of career growth for the employees so that they will be guided to reduce if not to eliminate problems in the organization.

Further, the results of the study may guide the chief in every municipal police station of Palawan for the implementation of activities and strategy that influence the subordinates to be more committed and increase the level of performance on work. Then, it may also give impact to officers to pursue their career

growth and eventually be more devoted to the organization. Furthermore, this may show and convince the community that the non-commissioned women officers who maintain peace and order are reliable. This may strengthen the public trust.

Lastly, researchers persuade for new ideas that will enhance employee's career growth. Future researchers may also conduct a research on the same nature with this but may add other variables not included in the present study.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined theoretically and operationally.

Career growth. It refers to the opportunity for development and advancement regarding *career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth, promotion equity* and *job rotation* as perceived by the non-commissioned women officers within the Philippine National Police.

Organizational commitment. It refers to the employee's psychological bond to the organization, sense of job involvement, loyalty, and belief in the values (Hundiwala, 2018). In this study, this refers to the affective, continuance and normative commitment of non-commissioned women officers in the Philippine National Police organization that helps them in the performance of their work.

METHODS

This chapter presents and describes the type of the research design that was utilized, the respondents of the study, the research instruments as well as the data gathering procedure and statistical treatment in the study.

Research Design

The study employed the quantitative non-experimental research design using the descriptive-correlation technique. It was seen appropriate for this study to use descriptive method because it focuses on fact-finding to establish the nature of something as it exists and can be used to find new characteristics, meanings or relationships in already existing data (Hakansson, 2013). Correlation method is a non-experimental design, which seeks to identify relationships that exist among variables and establishing relationships between two or more variables in the same population or between the same variables in two populations (Creswell, 2005; Leedy & Ormrod, 2010). In addition, correlation method was the most appropriate research design because it identified the significant relationship between career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment in Palawan.

Research Locale

The venue of the study is in the Province of Palawan. It has 1,700 islands in western part of the Philippines. Located on the MIMAROPA region, the island is called as the Philippine's last frontier. The province capital is Puerto Princesa City.

Figure 2. Map of the Philippines highlighting Palawan

It has 23 municipalities namely; Aborlan, Agutaya, Araceli, Balabac, Bataraza, Brooke's Point, Busuanga, Cagayancillo, Coron, Culion, Cuyo, Dumarán, El Nido, Kalayaan, Linapacan, Magsaysay, Narra, Quezon, Rizal, Roxas, San Vicente, Sofronio Española, and Taytay. Hence, the study was conducted in Palawan because the ideal number of non-commissioned women officers

has been overtaken due to less number of them in the Philippine National Police Organization in the province.

Population and Sample

Universal sampling was used in determining the total population and selection of the respondents. The researcher obtained 182 out of 297 non-commissioned women officers population as the total number of non-commissioned women officers involved in the study. Universal sampling is referred to as the selection of sample where not all the people in the population have the same probability of being included in the sample and the probability of being selected is unknown. The subjects of the study were the non-commissioned women officers in Palawan. The researcher believed that the non-commissioned women officers are the suitable respondents wherein they can answer the general and specific research objectives of the study.

Thus, all the non-commissioned women officers who have been assigned in Palawan were the subjects of this study. Correspondingly, no individual subject should be excluded without proper justification or requirement to do so. All the respondents have the prerogative for voluntary participation and have the right to withdraw from the research study. The study began on the 1st week of October up to the 2nd week of November, 2017 otherwise, after the questionnaire has been validated and upon approval of review committee. The actual respondents of the study were composed of 297 non-commissioned women officers from Provincial and City police headquarters and municipal police stations, and city sub-police office.

Research Instrument

There were two sets of survey questionnaire used in this study. The first set of the tool assessed the independent variable which is the level of career growth was adopted from Ku Daud (2014) which was modified to fit the context of the study and subjected to the validation by a panel of experts. Career growth of non-commissioned women officers had the following indicators: *career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth, promotion equity and job rotation.*

In evaluating career growth, the respondents indicated their answers on five-point Likert scale that ranges from 5 to 1 corresponding from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Additionally, the scale was used to determine the choice for a response to each item in the questionnaire.

Consequently, the scale with five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	very high	This means that the career growths of non-commissioned women officers are observed at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the career growths of non-commissioned women officers are observed oftentimes.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the career growths of non-commissioned women officers are observed sometimes.
1.80 – 2.59	low	This means that the career growths of non-commissioned women officers are observed seldom.
1.00 – 1.79	very low	This means that the career growths of non-commissioned women officers are never observed at all.

The second set of the instrument evaluated the dependent variable, which is the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers, which was also adapted from Ku Daud (2014). It was modified to fit into the context of the study and subjected to the validation by the panel of experts. Organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers had the following indicators: *affective commitment*, *continuance commitment*, and *normative commitment* (Nazneen & Miralam, 2017).

In evaluating the commitment of non-commissioned women officers, the following range of means with its descriptions was used.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	very high	This means that the non-commissioned women officers are committed at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the non-commissioned women officers are committed oftentimes.
2.60 – 3.39	moderate	This means that the non-commissioned women officers are sometimes committed.

1.80 – 2.59	low	This means that the non-commissioned women officers are seldom committed.
1.00 – 1.79	very low	This means that the non-commissioned women officers are never committed at all.

The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to the panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments, and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data.

Data Collection

After the approval of the panel members, the researcher went through the following steps and procedures in gathering data for the study. The researcher wrote a letter seeking permission from the Provincial Director of Palawan Police Office, PSSUPT Gabriel Cruz Lopez, and from the City Director of Puerto Princesa Police Office, PSSUPT Ronnie Francis M Cariaga. Immediately after the approval of the Provincial Director and the City Director, the researcher submitted the endorsement letters to the sub-police office of Puerto Princesa Police Office and Municipal Police Office, and consequently asked permission from the various chief of police from different sub-station and municipal police stations to distribute the research instrument to non-commissioned women officers.

Then, the researcher visited all police stations in Palawan to orient non-commissioned women officers' respondents about the purpose and significance of the study. The researcher personally distributed and administered the research instruments on career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment and some were sent on-line to the police station websites to ensure retrieval of the questionnaires. The respondents were given five to ten calendar days to answer the questionnaire given to them.

Subsequent to the given period of ten calendar days, the questionnaires were retrieved for tabulation. In order to make sure that the questionnaires could be retrieved at a hundred percent, again, the researcher went back to all the police stations in which the questionnaires were distributed and retrieved them. The researcher personally thanked the respondents for their valuable effort in answering the questionnaire. After the questionnaires were gathered, the data were collated, tabulated and tallied before they were subjected to statistical treatment, analysis, and interpretations, answering the research problems presented in Chapter 1.

Statistical Tools

The following statistical tools were used in interpreting the data collated.

Mean. This was used to describe the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient. This statistical tool was used to determine the significance of the relationship between career growth of non-commissioned women officers and their organizational commitment.

Regression. This statistical tool was used to determine the domains of the career growth that significantly influenced the organizational commitment.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher's proposal and questionnaires were examined by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee including the ethical procedures which will be followed in the conduct of the study particularly in managing the respondents and data gathered, but not limited to.

Voluntary participation. Wherein all the non-commissioned women officers involved were given the free will to participate without any form of consequences or penalty. Afterwards, the purpose and the benefits of the study were presented to the non-commissioned women officers respondents and their rights to contribute to the study was carefully considered. However, there were non-commissioned women officers who withdraw to participate in the study and in this case, they have revealed their reasons to the researcher, but after all, they were not really required to provide their reasons.

Privacy and confidentiality. The respondents' personal information including all other data gathered from them that was required in the study was kept private and utmost confidentiality of the same was adhered upon strictly.

Informed consent process. The researcher's questionnaire was free of technical terms and was easily understandable to the non-commissioned women officers of the study. The questionnaires have been administered with the consent and support of the authorities of the Philippine National Police, the Provincial Director of Palawan and the City Director of Puerto Princesa. Therefore, no research questionnaire has been given to any non-commissioned women officers without permission from the authorized command channels.

The Informed consent process involved providing sufficient information and assurances about the study to allow the non-commissioned women officers to understand the implications of participation and to reach a fully informed, and freely given decision about whether or not to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion.

Recruitment. Information about the study was presented to the potential non-commissioned women officers prior to their participation to help them establish their interest and willingness to serve as research subjects. Since it is significant that the information clearly and accurately represents the research, recruitment of them was handled in an ethical manner.

Risks. The study did not involve higher risk situations that the population may experience in the area of physical, psychological, or socio-economic concerns.

Benefits. This study was useful to the Philippine National Police officials, uniformed personnel, and non-uniformed personnel who may use the results in formulating and developing a system and a program on how to motivate police officers to become more committed in work and in the organization. Moreover, this may serve a point of reference in selecting the most appropriate factors of career growth for the employees so that they will be guided to reduce if not to eliminate problems in the organization.

Plagiarism, Fabrication, and Falsification. On the other hand, the study did not use any representations that will cause misrepresentation and plagiarism. With the use of Grammarly, Turnitin software and/or any plagiarism detector, consistency of grammar and minimization of the similarity index were ensured, giving the researcher the leeway in using his own words to express the idea anchored from the authors of different studies. Likewise, the study was anchored from different studies which were accurate and reliable. It ensured that researcher did not make any tale from his literature and thus, stating the idea of the authors out form his own idea and understanding.

Nevertheless, the study did not exaggerate the data and/or over claiming the works of others just to make the work fit. Models and theoretical framework used come from accurate and reliable sources. The study indicates a cautious and comprehensive track of sources. The researcher has accurately copied the author, title, and other information about the source publication, including the number(s) of the page(s) from which notes or quotes were taken. The researcher had thoroughly read and understood the importance of research integrity. The researcher followed honesty and integrity in order to avoid research misconduct.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher has adhered the institutional and governmental requirements for identifying, disclosing, and managing conflicts of interest. Although it is not possible to avoid all sources of conflict, it was in the best interest of the researcher to recognize

conflicts of interest and to take steps to nullify or mitigate those conflicts. Those conflicts that cannot be avoided have been disclosed by the researcher. At minimum, the institution and any other parties with a significant interest should be made aware of the extent and nature of the conflict.

Deceit. Moreover, with regard to the protection of non-commissioned women officers, it was noted that this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, and specifically, in either recruiting the participants, or methods of data collection. All non-commissioned women officers were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process.

Permission from Organization/Location. Before the researcher got to the stage of asking permission from potential research participants themselves, she assured the permission or approval of the head of agency or organization to conduct her study inside their vicinity. As governance arrangements for research have become more common, formal permission is increasingly likely to be required before formally conducting the study.

Authorship. The researcher proponent observed strict adherence to the scientific method. The research proponent made sure to make a detailed recordkeeping, meaningful and cleared delineation of collaboration, and shared understanding of authorship roles and responsibilities along with the research adviser's supervision. This study gives assurance to the participants that data provided were no maleficence that may incur harm that will affect the well-being of the participants. The researcher had also drafted the article and revised critically for important intellectual content and final approval of the version published.

Further, the adviser being the co-author of this study has also the responsibility and accountability for the results. The adviser is responsible for ensuring that all the authors' contact details are correct.

RESULTS

Presented in this chapter are the data and analysis of the findings based on the data collected from the research instruments used in the study to determine the influence of career growth of non-commissioned women officers on their organizational commitment in Palawan. Discussions of topics were engaged in the following subheadings: the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers, the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers, correlations between measures and the significance influence of career growth of non-commissioned women officers on their organizational commitment.

Level of Career Growth of Non-commissioned Women Officers

The first objective of this study was to assess the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers as perceived by the officers themselves. The level of career growth is regarding *career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth, promotion equity and job rotation*.

Shown in Table 1 are the data on the level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers. The level of career growth of non-commissioned women officers gets an overall mean of 3.70 or *high* with a standard deviation of 0.515. This means that the career growth of non-commissioned women officers was agreed in the PNP organization as providing good opportunities to realize career goals and encourages officers to continuously gain new job related knowledge.

Table 1
Level of Career Growth of Non-commissioned Women Officers

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
<i>Career Goal Progress</i>	0.750	4.16	High
<i>Professional Ability Development</i>	0.762	4.19	High
<i>Promotion Speed</i>	0.918	3.30	Moderate
<i>Remuneration Growth</i>	0.823	3.23	Moderate
<i>Promotion Equity</i>	0.743	3.52	High
<i>Job Rotation</i>	0.718	3.78	high
Overall	0.515	3.70	high

From this result, *professional ability development* has the highest mean score of 4.19 or *high*, which means that it is often manifested in the PNP organization. *Career goal progress* is the second highest indicator with a mean score of 4.16 or *high* with a standard deviation of 0.750, which means that it is agreed by the non-commissioned women officers to have been manifested in PNP organization. Subsequently, the third highest indicator is *job rotation* with a mean score of 3.78 or *high* and with a standard deviation of 0.718. On the other hand, *promotion equity, promotion speed, and remuneration growth* obtained mean ratings ranging from 3.52 or *high*, 3.30 or *moderate*, and 3.23 or *moderate* respectively.

Level of Organizational Commitment of Non-Commissioned Women Officers

The second objective was to ascertain the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: *affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment* of police officers.

Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. Computations had an overall mean of 3.84 or *high* with a standard deviation of 0.604 and this indicates that the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers is often manifested.

From this result, the indicator of the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers that yielded the highest mean score is the *normative commitment* with a mean score of 4.01 or *high* and a standard deviation of 0.662. Similarly, this also indicates that organizational commitment regarding *normative commitment* is often manifested. The second highest mean is the *affective commitment* with a mean score of 3.82 or *high* and a standard deviation of 0.614. This meant that the non-commissioned women officers are organizationally committed oftentimes. Finally, *continuance commitment* is the indicator with the lowest mean score of 3.69 albeit *high* and with standard deviation of 0.820.

Table 2
Level of Organizational Commitment of Non-commissioned Women Officers

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
<i>Affective Commitment</i>	0.614	3.82	high
<i>Continuance Commitment</i>	0.820	3.69	high
<i>Normative Commitment</i>	0.662	4.01	high
Overall	0.604	3.84	high

Significance on the Relationship between Career Growth of Non-Commissioned Women Officer and their Organizational Commitment

The most important purpose of this study was to ascertain whether the career growth of non-commissioned women officers is significantly related to their organizational commitment. Results of the computations are shown in Table 3. The overall R-value on the correlation between the level of career growth and the level of organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers was 0.386 with p-value less than 0.05. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, there was a significant relationship between the career growth and organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

When the domains of career growth were correlated with the overall organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers, the data showed that career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion equity and job rotation was significantly correlated with the organizational commitment with p-value less than 0.05 except the indicator on promotion speed and remuneration growth.

Table 3
Significance on the Relationship between Career Growth of Non-Commissioned Women Officer and their Organizational Commitment

Career Growth	Organizational Commitment
---------------	---------------------------

	Affective Commitment	Continuance Commitment	Normative Commitment	Overall
Career Goal Progress	0.342* (0.000)	0.220* (0.015)	0.420* (0.000)	0.369* (0.000)
Professional Ability Development	0.342* (0.000)	0.223* (0.014)	0.369* (0.000)	0.352* (0.000)
Promotion Speed	0.048 (0.599)	-0.015 (0.872)	0.037 (0.689)	0.023 (0.801)
Remuneration Growth	0.204* (0.024)	0.107 (0.242)	0.159 (0.080)	0.176 (0.053)
Promotion Equity	0.283* (0.002)	0.162 (0.075)	0.067 (0.467)	0.194 (0.032)
Job Rotation	0.507* (0.000)	0.333* (0.000)	0.406* (0.000)	0.471* (0.000)
Overall	0.422* (0.000)	0.249* (0.006)	0.357* (0.000)	0.386* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Furthermore, when each indicator of organizational commitment was correlated with the overall career growth, result revealed that all indicators of organizational commitment showed significant relationship with probability values less than 0.05.

Significance of the Influence of Career Growth on Organizational Commitment of Non-commissioned Women Officers

Shown in Table 4 are the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of the overall career growth on the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. Using the Regression Analysis, the data revealed that the overall career growth best influences the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers since the influences of career growth on the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers has the F value 7.20 and $p < 0.05$.

This meant that career growth of non-commissioned women officers best influences their organizational commitment since the p-value is less than 0.05. The R² value of 0.523 implies that 52.30 percent of the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers was influenced by their career growth while the remaining 47.70 percent was influenced by other factors not covered in this study. The overall results of the career growth of non-commissioned women officers predict their organizational commitment. Hence, it signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis. Specifically, the data revealed that the

domain of career growth which has the significant influence on organizational commitment is the job rotation, $t=4.06$, $p=0.000$, since the probability value of less than the alpha value.

Furthermore, in their singular capacity, job rotation best influences the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. However, the rest like career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed,

Table 4
Linear Regression Analysis of the Influence of Career Growth on Organizational Commitment of Non-commissioned Women Officers

Career Growth	Organizational Commitment			
	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.
Constant				
<i>Career Goal Progress</i>	0.1741	0.1137	1.53	0.129
<i>Professional Ability Development</i>	0.0056	0.1120	0.05	0.960
<i>Promotion Speed</i>	-0.04644	0.06229	-0.74	0.459
<i>Remuneration Growth</i>	0.04158	0.07450	0.56	0.578
<i>Promotion Equity</i>	0.01932	0.07619	0.25	0.800
<i>Job Rotation</i>	0.31743	0.07824	4.06	0.000
R	0.273			
R²	0.523			
F	7.20			
P	0.000			

remuneration growth and *promotion equity* can influence the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers but with the support of the other indicators.

DISCUSSION

Presented in this chapter are the discussions, conclusions, and recommendations derived from the results of the study.

Career Growth of Non-commissioned Women Officers

The high level of career growth is due to the high rating given by the respondents on professional ability development, career goal progress, promotion equity and job rotation. This signifies that non-commissioned women officers agreed that trainings are being provided often in the Philippine National Police. This is congruent to the view of Reyes and Conde (2017) to where they pointed out that employees who perceive professional ability development high usually believe that their current occupation encourages them to continuously gain new and job-related skills, new job-related knowledge, accumulate richer work experiences and enables them to continuously improve their professional capabilities (Karavardar, 2014; Spagnoli et al. 2019). Likewise, the non-commissioned women officers believed that their job is providing them with good opportunities to realize career goals. This result is similar to the views of various authors (Wang et al. 2014; Weng & McElroy, 2012; Weng et al. 2010), that career growth helps the employees feel the security in their position within their organization.

Organizational Commitment of Non-commissioned Women Officers

The high level of organizational commitment is due to the high rating given by the respondents on affective, continuance and normative commitment. This indicates that non-commissioned women officers have high desires, needs and obligation to work with the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1997; Yucel, Mcmillan & Richard, 2014). It implies that for them leaving the organization is not right even it were to their advantage, as the organization deserves their loyalty. It signifies that they are contented with their career in the organization, which has a great deal of personal bearing (Cai et al. 2017) to them while considering its problems as their problems. The result is supported by the statement of Ku Daud (2014) who pointed out that a person is tied up to the organization once he or she has commitment, which no matter what happens to the said organization, that person will remain loyal and obliged to serve the organization.

Significance on the Relationship between Career Growth of Non-Commissioned Women Officer and their Organizational Commitment

The correlation between the two variables reveals a significant relationship between the career growth and organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. This implies that the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers is relative with their career growth. The career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion equity and job rotation affect their commitment to their organization. Further, it means that the career growth of non-commissioned women officers plays a significant aspect in augmenting their commitment to the organization particularly on affective, continuance and normative commitment. Thus, non-commissioned women officers need a particular career growth in such a way that greater the level of career growth they have, the higher will be their commitment with the organization.

This finding of the study corroborates with Weng et al. (2010), Weng and Mc Elroy (2012) and Ku Daud (2014) who state that there is a significant relationship between career growth and organizational commitment. This shows the important role of career growth of non-commissioned women officers in developing organizational commitment. Hence, it exemplifies the notion how career growth of non-commissioned women officers may affect their organizational commitment.

Furthermore, this confirms the claim of Hu et al., (2008) and Chen et al. (2015) that career growth should always be considered in making decisions, as it is associated with the organizational commitment. The result further affirms the idea that career growth will help the organization develop and convince its employee continue to remain in the company and achieve the organizational goals.

Significance of the Influence of Career Growth on Organizational Commitment of Non-commissioned Women Officers

A regression analysis was employed to determine which domain of career growth best influences the organizational commitment of non-commissioned women officers. Data revealed that the overall career growth best influences their organizational commitment. This corroborates with the proposition of Ku Daud (2014), who pointed out that career growth significantly influences the organizational commitment.

Furthermore, this finding is in line with the proposition of Weng et al. (2010) that career growth significantly influences commitments of non-commissioned women officers. This also confirmed that organizational commitment is positively related to career growth that enhances the very important tool of the employees in doing their job, the discretion and knowledge (Ganter, & Hecker, 2014).

In particular, the data revealed that in the singular capacities, job rotation could significantly influence the organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers. However, the rest, includes career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth and promotion equity can also influence organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers but with the support of the other indicators. This means that there is a significant influence of job rotation on organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers and it implies that non-commissioned women officers become more committed in the organization when they are transferred to various fields to broaden their knowledge and skills throughout the organization. The assertion of diverse authors (Chen et al. 2013; Khan et al. 2014; Ku Daud, 2014; Saravani & Abbasi, 2013) show that job rotation is related to commitment and increase the performance level of employees.

CONCLUSION

The overall level of career growth is high which means that the non-commissioned women officers oftentimes observed it in the organization. Its indicators reveal the following results: high for professional ability development, for career goal progress, for job rotation, for promotion equity, and moderate for promotion speed and remuneration growth. Similarly, the overall level of organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers is high.

Moreover, there is a significant relationship between the career growth and organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers since the p-value is of less than 0.05. Further, the overall career growth of non-commissioned women officers best influences their organizational commitments. In their singular capacities, job rotation can significantly influence the organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers. However, the rest like career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, remuneration growth and promotion equity can influence the organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers but with the support of the other indicators.

This study supports the anchor proposition (Weng et al., 2010) that career growth significantly influences commitments. This proposition was measured because it gives the viewpoint on how career growth may affect the organizational commitment to performing and carrying out their duties and responsibilities in achieving the goals and objectives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study revealed a high career growth and organizational commitments of non-commissioned women officers. Therefore, the researcher recommends that the provincial, the city director and the chief of police may further monitor through surveys and researches the interest, needs, and situations and even the stigma experienced by non-commissioned women officers. This will help them to be fully aware what necessary actions and support they have to offer to maintain or increase a high career growth and organizational commitments. Likewise, continues reorientation and promotion of police ethics and values among police officers are highly recommended to increase their sense of obligation as public servants.

The researcher also recommends that the PNP officials should revisit their programs and activities for personnel and reconsidered factors that include providing more opportunities for officers to realize their career goals, gain knowledge and specialized skills and trainings, fair policies, rules and regulations for promotion and job rotation in various fields. They must continuously improve the system and practice of job rotation in various fields of policing.

Subsequently, albeit the finding of the research shows a significant influence of career growth of non-commissioned women officers towards their organizational commitments, the researcher still recommends that there may be supplementary researches on the other factors that are associated with the organization. More studies may be conducted to support the findings of the study.

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